

Biography: Uno Eliasson

Carlos Rojas¹

¹ Department of Biosystems Engineering, University of Costa Rica, San Pedro de Montes de Oca, 11501, Costa Rica

E-mail: carlos.rojasalvarado@ucr.ac.cr

Received: 1 April 2023

Accepted for publication: 7 May 2023

Published: 19 June 2023

Editor: Steven L. Stephenson

Abstract: Professor Uno Eliasson, based in Sweden, has been one of the noteworthy contributors to the advancement of myxomycete science in contemporary times. He also has worked extensively with vascular plants. In this short biography, a glimpse of his career is provided and some of his most prominent publications are listed.

Keywords: Galapagos Islands, Hawaii, Sweden.

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Professor Uno Eliasson (Fig. 1) was born in 1939 in Alingsås, Sweden. He carried out his studies on zoology, botany, and limnology at the universities of Gothenburg and Lund. His thesis, in 1974, focused on the vascular plant flora of the Galapagos Islands and was carried out at the University of Gothenburg.

He ultimately became a Professor of Taxonomic Botany at the university and in 1999 he became the Director and Head Curator of the Botanical Museum and Herbarium GB, at the University of Gothenburg, Sweden. He was affiliated with this herbarium during the period between 1985 and 2004.

His main research interests have included (1) island biology, (2) Neotropical vascular plant taxonomy, and (3) the taxonomy and ecology of myxomycetes. Most of his field work took place in different locations in both Europe and United States, but also in Cuba, Jamaica, Ecuador, the Galapagos Islands and the Hawaiian Islands. He was an active researcher in the All Taxa Biological Inventory project carried out in the Great Smoky Mountains National Park in the United States.

He became a Professor Emeritus of the University of Gothenburg in 2004.

Selected publications on vascular plants

Eliasson UH. 1974. Studies in Galapagos Plants. XIV. The Genus *Scalesia* Arn. Opera Bot. 36: 1-117.

Eliasson UH. 1984. Native climax forests in the Galápagos Islands. In: Perry R, ed. Key environments: Galápagos. Oxford: Pergamon Press. pp. 101-114.

Eliasson UH. 1987. Amaranthaceae. In: Harling G and Andersson L, eds. Flora of Ecuador 28. Sweden: Department of Systematic Botany, Göteborg University and Museum of Natural History, Stockholm. pp. 138.

Eliasson UH. 1993. Phytolaccaceae, Achatocarpaceae. In: Harling G and Andersson L, eds. Flora of Ecuador 46. Sweden: Department of Systematic Botany, Göteborg University and Museum of Natural History, Stockholm. pp. 52.

Eliasson UH. 1996. Molluginaceae, Aizoaceae, Portulacaceae. In: Harling G Andersson L, eds. Flora of Ecuador 55. Sweden: Department of Systematic Botany, Göteborg University, and Museum of Natural History, Stockholm. pp. 1-53.

Eliasson UH. 1988. Floral morphology and taxonomic relations among the genera of Amaranthaceae in the New World and the Hawaiian Islands. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society (London)* 96: 235-283.

Eliasson UH. 2004. The evolutionary patterns of the plant family Amaranthaceae on the Galápagos and Hawaiian Islands. *Journal of the Torrey Botanical Society* 131: 105-109.

Figure 1. Professor Uno Eliasson showing the myxomycete collection at the herbarium of the University of Gothenborg

Selected publications on myxomycetes

Eliasson UH. 1977. Recent advances in the taxonomy of Myxomycetes. *Botaniska Notiser* 130: 483-492.

Eliasson UH, Lundqvist N. 1979. Fimicolous myxomycetes. *Botaniska Notiser* 132: 551-568.

Eliasson UH. 1981. Patterns of occurrence of myxomycetes in a spruce forest in south Sweden. *Holarctic Ecology* 4: 20-31.

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